

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TRAORE****FIRST NAME: IBRAHIMA SORY DIABA****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied xUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2024, 6-14)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
3. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

Last November, I had the honor of being accepted into Euclid University for a Ph.D. in Epidemiology-Biostatistics. When I received the acceptance email, I felt immense joy as I had just achieved one of my greatest dreams. From that day, I was convinced that my professional career was about to take a new turn. However, I also knew I would need much effort to succeed.

Upon receiving the first documents shared by the university, I immediately understood that serious work was beginning and that I would need to organize myself to be effective. I started by carefully reading the orientation documents that were sent to me. After activating my CMS and LMS accounts, I watched the ACA-401 video several times. Then, I downloaded the course documents for the first period and began reading the coursepack for period one.

The period one coursepack delivers essential guidance for both international academics and professionals on the fundamentals of paper writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 3).

Writing is important because it is used extensively in higher education and in the workplace. If students do not know how to express themselves in writing, they will not be able to communicate well with professors, employers, peers, or just about anyone else (Blanka 2012, 9).

Thus, in this first period, I present my reflection and understanding of five key concepts from the Packperiod1 document: essay writing, punctuation, American vs. British English, plagiarism, and the style guide.

2) ESSAY WRITING

This first chapter is of paramount importance as it highlights the essential elements of an academic essay, including the basics of writing, the steps of a good essay, and the fundamental rules for writing a scientific article. These elements ensure the relevance and quality of an essay. Among the many types of essays, this chapter focuses on academic essays, which are non-fictional writings produced as part of university work.

It is a crucial step that clarifies the flexibility of the stages of writing an academic essay. Starting early is crucial for writing a good essay; the sooner you begin, the higher the chances of producing a quality essay. It is also essential to thoroughly understand and analyze the topic from different angles. All this work should be reflected in a well-structured plan, with initial reflections on the research topic forming the preliminary outline of the essay.

In addition to thoroughly understanding the topic, it is crucial to conduct a literature review to find the necessary elements for writing. This involves reading extensively without rushing; the more information you have, the easier the writing process becomes. While reading, always keep the topic or question of the essay clearly in mind and note that you must use sound evidence to support your argument. Therefore, spend much time looking for relevant information (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 9). It is also important to remember that all document sources must have references following a precise style that includes the author's name, date, title, publisher, place of publication, and other relevant details. After these readings, it will be necessary to organize the ideas well and start drafting an essay plan that determines how to answer the research question and structure the essay.

Regarding essay writing, I noted that the first step is to produce a first draft following the plan previously developed. Once this draft is written, the rest becomes more straightforward, as it is a matter of adding details to improve the content of the essay. I also noted that the structure of an essay includes three essential parts: the introduction, the body, and the conclusion. Each part follows a specific writing style to achieve the desired objective. For example, the introduction should move from general to specific, introducing the topic with a broad and general opening sentence.

The essay's body consists of paragraphs, each contributing to the construction of the argument. It is important to present ideas and evidence to develop the argument. Finally, unlike the introduction, the conclusion moves from specific to general. This part

should restate the answer to the question, summarize the main points, and include a final, general statement. I also noted that all academic essays must include references. Only references protect against plagiarism, a serious academic offense. It is, therefore, essential to understand the referencing style used by the school or journal. In some situations, specific guidelines are provided on the referencing standard to use. EUCLID, for example, accepts any form of reference as long as it is rigorous and consistent.

Finally, I noted that it is crucial to thoroughly understand and follow the course guidelines meticulously when submitting the essay while meeting the teachers' requirements.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

After reading this section, I understood that punctuation, often considered trivial, is paramount in essay writing. I also noted that it is essential to know all punctuation marks and their usage and to distinguish between correct and incorrect punctuation. According to EUCLID, one should use the least punctuation necessary while maintaining the sentence's meaning.

I understood the strict conditions for using parentheses, periods, colons, and semicolons. For example, I use parentheses to add additional information, translations, dates, explanations, or definitions. Colons are used to introduce a subclause that follows logically from the text before it, is not a new concept, and depends logically on the preceding main clause (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 18). I also gained sufficient information on the use of commas, dashes, and hyphens.

I noted many punctuation marks, each with strict usage conditions. When writing an essay, reviewing the punctuation usage guidelines and making the necessary corrections is crucial. I understood that rigorous use of punctuation is part of the quality criteria for a scientific essay.

Finally, I know that using punctuation is a significant challenge in essay writing, but I can use it with more concentration and rigor according to the requirements. I also understand that I should only use them when necessary.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

I come from a French-speaking country where I completed all my schooling and university studies. During my English courses, I learned the fundamental differences between American English and British English. I knew there were differences in pronunciation, spelling, and sometimes the meaning of words. However, I learned that these differences had to be considered in writing scientific documents, and these two types of English could not be used together in the same essay. It is important to choose one of the two from the beginning of the writing process.

American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with "educated" or "scientific" English. Most divergence can be ascribed to differing national histories and cultural development (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25). I learned that it is crucial to be rigorous and to use only one type of English throughout the writing process. For this, it is important to master the main differences between standard American English and standard British English.

5) PLAGIARISM

First and foremost, it is important to understand that as a student, I must produce authentic work demonstrating my understanding of the research topic. According to Euclid, plagiarism occurs when an author uses a source of information without crediting the original author. According to Harvard College, in academic writing, it is considered plagiarism to use someone else's idea or language without adequately crediting that source in your document. Universities take plagiarism very seriously, as committing it risks my reputation and future opportunities. Therefore, I will take care to avoid it in all my writings.

Fortunately, this concept is not unfamiliar to me, as we thoroughly covered this topic in medical school while preparing my thesis and during my master's dissertation in epidemiology. For any professional aspiring to a long and inspiring career, it is crucial to avoid plagiarism. The best way to make sure you do not plagiarize due to confusion or carelessness is to understand what you are doing when you write a paper and follow a method that is systematic and careful as you do your research (Derenencourt 2022, 18).

However, I noted that there are circumstances where citation is not necessary. For example, When the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas, you do not need to cite its source (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 37).

6) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to some aspects of writing style that need to be consistent (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41). I have also noted that it is important to be consistent in writing style for any writing. The writing style can vary from one project to another or from one author to another. Having had the opportunity to write in French and English, I have understood that the writing style can also vary according to the language. I have also learned that the writing style develops over time. It must be built and maintained until it becomes memorable, identifiable, and recognizable.

Finally, I noted that different types of content determine writing styles, including magazines, books, scientific research, advertising, etc. The writing style, therefore, depends on the purpose of the content we want to write for our audience.

7) CONCLUSION

Scientific writing is an essential component of a Ph.D. It is crucial to master the fundamental aspects of good writing. Throughout this initial period, I have once again understood the importance of being rigorous and consistent in all my writings. Before writing an essay, it is essential to read extensively and research to gather enough elements to enrich my essay.

The course material from this first period has been very instructive for me. I am sure that I will continue to utilize it throughout my training, as I am convinced that the more I master its content, the better my chances of producing quality writing are.

REFERENCES

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